
APPLICATION AND USE OF E-CONTENT MATERIAL FOR BOOSTING THE
TEACHING AND LEARNING BY FACULTY MEMBERS OF AFFILIATED
COLLEGES OF SHIVAJI UNIVERSITY, KOLHAPUR

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Abstract:

The present study is focused on application and use of e-content material for boosting the teaching learning process of affiliated college faculty members of Shivaji University, Kolhapur. Due to the high cost of e-resource subscriptions, it is important to carefully consider their purpose and results. The goal of this study is to determine how well-informed, readily available, and utilised e-resources are by faculty. It also looks at the difficulties consumers have accessing online resources and how satisfied they are with them. The survey research method was used and structured questionnaire tool was used to collect the data from teachers. Out of 150 sampling teachers, 120 teachers were responded to the questionnaire. The data had been analyzed and considering the finding, suggestions had given to conduct the Orientation program, install the digital library management software and provide the updated online services to the users of the library.

Keywords: E-Resources, Faculty usage, e-journals, Internet, Information and Communication Technology etc.

Introduction:

Higher education has made tremendous growth for providing quality education in India. Information and communication technology have come to play a central role in education. Tremendous print and non-print material had been coming in knowledge domain. E-content and sources are becoming more and more important and helpful for the academic community. Academic community relies on recent and timely information. Electronic resources are now preferred and used more often than print resources. Faculty members benefit from

these resources as well, by employing a series of useful tools.

Information that a user might not have access to due to their location or financial limitations is made available through electronic resources. Because they are frequently updated, electronic resources also give users access to current information. Electronic resources offer a wealth of links to discover related or extra materials through their various search methods. Additionally, electronic resources are valued as crucial tools for training, research, and teaching. As a result, the majority of today's universities and libraries offer online tools for learning

and research. Information is delivered through electronic resources such as full-text databases, electronic journals, image collections, multimedia on CD, tape, the internet, and the online, among other formats. Online journals, conversations, news, data archives, email, chat rooms, and other electronic resources are examples of e-resources.

To redefine the collection and services offered by academic libraries and to enhance the technological platforms that make these electronic contents accessible to users, there is a critical need to research the usage of electronic resources and look into the degree of satisfaction among academics.

Review of the Literature:

The researchers have reviewed the related material to understand the previous research in the present study and decided the direction of research. The present reviews give the proper direction to complete the present survey.

Lohar and Roopashree (2006), investigated how faculty members are using electronic resources to advance their academic careers as well as the issues that come up when using these resources. The study solely included academic members.

Lohar and Kumbar (2007), study's findings showed that 52.25% of users only spent over 30 minutes and less than an hour per week in libraries. A very tiny percentage of users were aware of the interlibrary lending programme. The usability of the reading material, its suitability, and users' perceptions of library services, including orientation, computerization of libraries, the Internet, interlibrary loans, and photocopying services, were also looked at.

Patil and Parameshwar (2009), highlighted the use of e-resources by the

faculty members and research scholars in Gulbarga University. Questionnaire tool was used for data collection. The study found that there is need to train the users for better utilization of e-content material.

Nisha And P. M. (2013), according to a survey on the use of e-journals, the majority of users are aware of their use and utilize them not only to expand and update their knowledge but also to gather pertinent information for their study and research purposes.

Rajenderkumar (2016), his study found that the majority of P.G. and U.G. students are aware of and utilise the online resources at MaharshiMarkandeshwar University, Ambala. Additionally, he discovered that online materials are more educational and that medical students are not generally satisfied with their usage of online resources.

Scope of the Study:

The present study is limited to the faculty members of affiliated colleges of Shivaji University, Kolhapur. This study is limited to Arts, Commerce and Science college teachers only. Out of the total teachers, 120 randomly selected teachers are considered for the study. The study highlights the awareness and availability and use of e-resources by the faculty members, problems faced while accessing e-resources, level of satisfaction of the users, suitable recommendations to improve facilities and services.

Objectives:

1. To understand the types of e- resources used by teachers for boosting the teaching and learning
2. To study the purposes and use of e-content material by teachers
3. To find out the problems in accessing the e-content material

4. To understand the satisfaction level of use of e-content material

Research Methodology:

Shivaji University, Kolhapur has 279 affiliated colleges. Among them 172 colleges were Arts, Commerce and Science colleges. The present study focuses on only Arts, Commerce and Science colleges. The researcher has used the survey method for present study. Total population were 120 teachers in the randomly selected from respective affiliated colleges. Total 150 teachers were contacted to fill the questionnaires. 120 teachers (80.00%) were responded for the present study.

Result and Discussion:

The researchers has analyzed & interpreted data by using tables, graphs in the light of frequency of usages of e-resources by faculty members in Arts, Commerce and Science colleges selected for present study. The Shivaji University, Kolhapur has 279 affiliated colleges and it was situated in three districts viz. Kolhapur, Sangali and Satara. The researchers have focused on Arts, Commerce and Science College teachers only. Out of Total population, only 5% (150) of the teachers are considered for the present survey.

District-wise distribution of Arts, Commerce & Science Colleges and Teachers

Table No 1: District-wise distribution of Arts, Commerce & Science Colleges and Teachers

Sr. No	District	Colleges	Teachers	Sampling	Response
1	Kolhapur	67	1218	62	42
2	Sangali	53	876	43	38
3	Satara	52	910	45	40
	Total	172	3004	150	120

The above table gives the clear picture of the sampling and response to the structured questionnaire. The researchers

had considered only 120 (80.00%) teachers for the present survey.

Frequency use of internet for educational purpose:

Graph No 1: Frequency use of internet for educational purpose by faculty members

The above graph indicates that 45.83% teachers are using daily the

Internet for educational purpose and 0% response for Rarely and Never is recorded.

Purpose of using e-content material:

Table No 2: Purpose of using e-content material by teachers

Sr. No.	Purpose of using e-content material	Response	Percentage
1	To prepare for teaching	85	70.83
2	For research	102	85.00
3	To Collect current information	78	65.00
4	To write a book / article / research paper	85	70.83
5	For entertainment	52	43.33
6	For referencing	45	37.50
7	To read newspapers	43	35.83
8	To study and learning	89	74.17
9	To access e-content material	78	65.00

The above table shows that 85% teachers using the e-content/ e-resources for research purpose. 74.17% teachers are giving preference to study and learning, 70.83% teachers using the e-content

material for to write a book/article/research paper and less preference i.e.35.83% teachers prefer to read e-newspapers.

Types of e-resources prefer for teaching and learning:

Graph No 2: Types of e-resources prefer for teaching and learning by the teachers

The above graph clearly indicates that teachers are giving more preference to E-books (90%) and E-journals (81.67%). They also prefer E-study Materials (71.67%) and E-encyclopedia (61.67%). Other remaining e-resources are preferred very less in percentage.

E-resources are more accessible than the printed material:

The majority of teachers (92%) are expressed their opinion that now a-days e-resources are more accessible than the printed material. It is easily accessible, readable and downloadable on various gadgets.

E-resources are really boosting your teaching and learning:

The 95% teachers are opined that in the technological era, e-resources are

really boosting the teaching and learning process. ICT is becoming the core part of teaching and learning system. Students are also involving and taking the keen interest

in ICT. Students can get the clear idea of his concept through the ICT tools. So the teachers are also giving more preference to e-resources.

Problems facing while accessing the e-content material :

Table No 3: Problems facing while accessing the e-content material

Sr. No	Problems	Yes	No
01	Don't know the proper method of accessing e-content material	90.00	10.00
02	Slow Internet speed	81.67	18.33
03	Uncomfortable to Study on Computer screen	75.00	25.00
04	Slow Downloading	72.50	27.50
05	Regional Language Problem	82.50	17.50
06	Lack of Time	56.67	43.33
07	Lack of Infrastructure	67.50	32.50
08	Lack of Training	87.50	12.50
09	Difficulty in finding relevant information	54.17	45.83
10	Information overload	45.83	54.17
11	Privacy problem	34.17	65.83
12	Popups and advertisements of unwanted websites	20.83	79.17
13	Other problems	8.33	91.67

The above table shows that 90% of teachers are opined that the major problem while accessing the e-content material is they don't know the proper method of accessing e-content material, 87.50%

teachers are saying lack of training and 81.67% teachers are saying the slow internet speed is also the major hurdle in accessing the e-content material.

Impact of e-resources on reading habit:

Table No.4 : Impact of e-resources on reading habit of the faculty members

Sr. No	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided
01	I like reading electronic resources	54.17%	31.67%	8.33%	4.17%	1.67%
02	It has improved my reading interest	38.33%	43.33%	4.17%	12.50%	1.67%
03	I am comfortable with electronic resources.	55.83%	26.67%	1.67%	13.33%	2.50%
04	It has improved my reading speed.	45.83%	30.00%	8.33%	10.00%	5.83%
05	It makes reading more Enjoyable	20.83%	15.83%	40.00%	20.00%	3.33%
06	Electronic resources waste my time	17.50%	14.17%	45.83%	17.50%	5.00%
07	It has increased my independency and self-learning skills	45.83%	31.67%	12.50%	7.50%	2.50%
08	E-resources develops my reading habit	50.83%	34.17%	10.83%	2.50%	1.67%

The above table indicates the positive impact of e-resources on the reading habit of the teachers. The statements which are strongly agreed by

majority of the teachers clearly indicate that e-resources improve the reading habit skill and the changed format of electronic media is accepted by the teachers.

Level of satisfaction about e-content services provided by your college library:

Out of 120 teachers, 95% (140) teachers are satisfied with the e-content service provided by their respective college libraries. The College libraries are providing their library services through Web portal and other media to the users.

Findings:

The present survey found following findings through the analysis.

1. 45.83% teachers of various colleges are using the Internet daily for educational purpose. Internet becomes the more prominent, updated and reliable source of Information.
2. Research is most important factor in education system. It always adding the new ideas or knowledge to the respective subject domain. It is observed that 85% teachers using the e-content/ e-resources for research purpose.
3. Majority of teachers are giving more preference to E-books (90%) and E-journals (81.67%). They also prefer E-study Materials (71.67%) and E-encyclopedia (61.67%) to get the desired information.
4. 92% teachers are giving preference to Non- printed materials.
5. The 95% teachers are expressed their views that e-resources are really boosting the teaching and learning process.
6. 85% teachers are facing the problem to access the e-resources is they don't know the proper method of accessing e-content material and lack of training for proper utilization.

7. Most of the teachers states positive impact of e-resources on the reading habit of the teachers.
8. 95% (140) teachers are satisfied with the e-content service provided by their respective college libraries.

Suggestions:

1. It is strongly recommended that the College Librarians should conduct the Library Orientation Programs on regular intervals especially for faculty members.
2. The College libraries should adopt the modern tools and renders the digital library services to their users.
3. The College library should use Digital Library Management softwares to manage the e-content.
4. The libraries should subscribe the e-resource consortia for library users like N-List.

Conclusion:

The present study is survey of application, utilization, awareness and level of satisfaction of e-resources of the faculty members of affiliated colleges of Shivaji University, Kolhapur. The emergence of new electronic devices and formats has been aided by the quick development of information and communication technology, particularly the internet and electronic resources. It altered the conventional approaches to scholarly information search, storage, retrieval, and transmission. Latest Information has been incorporated into numerous types of electronic resources in a number of different methods and formats. Faculty members today rely largely on electronic resources to get the information they need and to stay current in their fields. Therefore, libraries' importance in the era of electronic

resources has greatly expanded, especially in terms of educating and advising users on how to access reliable information. This study also gives the recommendation on the basis of analysis for further development of college Libraries.

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